

Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through
Interdisciplinary Practices in Management

An Overview on Personality Development

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ABSTRACT

This study is conceptualized from a theoretical background. This indicates that the current study to explore the knowledge of personality. In our culture with its emphasis on the importance of being liked by people, nothing is more important than 'Personality'. In modern popular sense personality is conceived by most as an intangible quality that make individual attractive or unattractive to his follows. This paper attempts an individual personality with theories and reviewing of literatures.

INTRODUCTION

Personality is the sum total of an individual physiology and psychology system that determinant of her behavior in a given environment. Human being have a mind and body both of which act or behave competitiveness and survival of organizations depend on their innovation capabilities of a person. Therefore organization are paying special attention on workforce to behave innovations and a relatively person. So there is a need to work our on the on tecedents enablers and predictors of innovative behavior innovative behavior is considered to be influenced by humerous personal and internal determinants

This study will intend to explore the relationship of personality of an individual and how personally of an individual different to answere this question pervious on this topic will be from theories and types in details.

So this study will review past studies books and internet on concept of personality and after discussing conclusion will give on this topic.

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Research methodology

In present study the research used the secondary data which is collected through review of literatures books and internet

psychophysical system that determines his unique adjustments to his environment.

Objectives

- 1. To understand the concept of personality development
- 2. To review past study related to personality development

Determinents of personality

Different thinkers have listened different determinants of personality this various determinents of personality are brodly classified into three groups

- 1. Heredity
- 2. Environment
- 3. Situation

Concept of personality

Personality means deferent thing of different people. Personality is based or the characteristic set of behavior cognition and emotional pattern that evolve from biological and environmental factors personality is so widely studied concept by the psychologists that personality psychology is taken as a separate discipline of psychology personality psychology is concerned with the analysis of human nature and throes surrounded by the personality. Suppose there are two persons of the same age but have different interests, activities feelings and thinking it mens there is something different inside them, inside is said to be personality all port presented the same concept of personality in his definitions the dynamic organizations with in the individual of those

Heredity

Heredity refers to biological factors such as qualities from the prents to the children through a biological mechanism physical stature facial attractiueness temperament sex etc, are the examples of heredity that are generally influenced by who ones parents

Parents → children ⇌ personality

Environment

Environment generated to a child also exerts important influence in shaping his/her personality research studied have also revealed that parents have more effect on the personality development of their children as compared to other members of the family the socialization process starts with the initial contact between a mother and her new infant. They in fact gradually come into contact with the social groups outside home/family such as peer, school friends and the members of the work group. Organization itself also contributes much to socialization.

Parents → children → Social Group → Personality

Situation

The heredity and environment are the primary determinants of personality but the situation that influence effect of heredity and environment on personality. And individual personality does change depending on the situation because of the different demands of the different situation from different aspects of one's personality for example

The same person while facing an employee and enjoying family life behave quite differently depending on two different situations. Hence personality needs to be looked at situational content not in isolation.

Parents → children → society → situation → personality

Types of personality

Following are the main types of personality

1. Introvert and extrovert personalities
2. Type A and type B personalities
3. Judging and perceptive personalities

Introvert personalities

Introvert persons with introvert orientation are primarily oriented to the subjective world. They look inward expending process their thoughts and ideas within themselves they also avoid social contacts and initiating interaction with other groups.

Extrovert personalities

Simply speaking extroverts are just contrary to introverts. They refer to the level of comfort ability with relationship to others it represents active assertive talkative outgoing social energetic and ambitious these people are good in active energy.

Type A and type B personalities

Type A- these people are characteristic by hard working highly achievement oriented impatient have sense of time urgency aggressive with competitive drive etc. such people are to be very productive.

Type B- easy-going sociable free from urgency of time non-competitive are characteristic of type B personality. Such people do better on tasks involving judgements accuracy rather than speed and team work.

Judging perceptive personalities

Judging

People with judging personalities type like to follow a plan make decisions and need only that what is essential for their work.

Perceptive

These are the people who well to change, want to know all about job and get overcommitted they tend to be curious and welcome new information on a thing or a situation.

Theories of personality

Personality theories are different from psychology field as well as from other fields dealing with human behavior the theories of personality have been grouped as

1. Psychoanalytic theory

This theory is developed by Sigmund Freud it is based on psychoanalytical theory. Which is based on that human behavior is influenced more by unseen forces than conscious and rational though Freud's clinical experiments on patients behavior is mainly influenced by unconscious framework this unconscious is composed of three elements

- A. The id - the id is innate and the source of psychic energy. It is immediate gratification for biological needs. The id follows the basic principle of all human life. The id is set of uncoordinated instinctual trends. Different levels of development and the relations to parental images correspond to specific id forms of aggression and affection e.g. to dismember to swallow whole to make disappear etc. the id by immediately reducing tension thus obeys the pleasure principle as id knows and obeys no laws and rules.
- B. The ego - the ego is conscious part while the id is unconscious part of human personality the ego is associated with reality it checks the id though logic and intellect the ego can best be described as controlling id though realities a starving man can control or satisfy his hunger simply by eating images but reality in satisfying hunger or reducing tension. The ego is the organized realistic part that mediates between the desire of the id and the super ego.
- C. The super ego - the super ego represents system of values norms and ethics that guide and govern a person to behave properly in the society. The super ego is conscience it provides norms and values to ego to determine what is wrong or right at a given time in given situation. The super ego judges whether an action behavior is right or wrong as per the set norms and standard of the society. So the id seeks pleasure the ego verifies reality and the super ego strives for perfection. Psychoanalytical theory is an analytic study of the human psyche outlining the id ego and super ego which is of fundamental importance in the development of psychoanalysis.

2. Socio-psychological theory

The socio-psychological theory asserts that individual and society are interlinked through this interaction the personality of an individual is determined the socio-psychological is the contribution of Adler, Horney, Fromm and Sullivan.

This theory is also called as neo-freudian theory because it differs from the Freud's psychoanalytic theory in the following respects.

1. According to this theory the social variables and not the biological instincts are the important determinants in shaping the individual's personality.
2. Here the motivation is conscious and individual knows what are his needs and wants and what kind of behavior is required to meet these needs.

Thus the theorists believe that socio-psychological factors the combination of both the social family, society, wealth religion and the psychological factors play an important role in shaping this personality and influences his behaviour according to the external situation.

3. Trait theory
Trait theory is an approach to the study of human personality. Trait theorists are primarily interested in the measurement of traits which can be defined as habitual patterns of behavior, thought and emotions.

- Trait theory of leadership differentiates leaders from non-leaders by focusing on personal qualities and characteristics.
- Trait theory of leadership sought personality, social, physical and intellectual traits.
- Trait theory assumes that leaders are born.

Trait theories of leadership

Thus trait theory of personality attempts to understand how a set of personality variables exerts on one's behavior

however this theory is very descriptive rather than analytical.

4. Self theory-
This theory is introduced by Carl Rogers of personality. Carl Rogers was a humanistic psychologist who agreed with the main assumption of Abraham Maslow but added that for a person to grow they need an environment that provides them with genuineness, acceptance (being seen with unconditional positive regard) and empathy (being listened to and understood).

The concept of personality development described by Rogers is the notion of self or self-concept. This is defined as the organized, consistent set of defined ideas about oneself. The self is the humanistic term for who we really are as a person. The self is our inner personality; the self is influenced by the experiences a person has in their life and our interpretations of those experiences. Two primary sources that influence our self-concept are childhood experience and evaluation by others.

The humanistic approach states that the self is composed of concepts unique to ourselves. The self-concept includes three components.

1. Self-worth
2. Self-image
3. Ideal-self

1. Self worth- Self-worth compares what we think about ourselves. Rogers believed that the feeling of self-worth developed in early childhood and was formed from the interaction of the child with the mother and father.

2. Self image- How we see ourselves, which is important to good psychological health. Self-image includes the influence of our body image on inner personality. At a simple level, we might perceive ourselves as good or bad, person, beautiful or ugly. Self-image affects how a person thinks, feels, and behaves in the world.

3. Ideal self- This is the person who we would like to be. It consists of our goals and ambitions in life and is dynamic, forever changing. The ideal self in childhood is not the ideal self in our teens or late twenties, etc. This is an attempt at analyzing and understanding organizational behavior; the self-concept plays a significant role in reacting in a particular manner.

How personality develops?

Personality develops with advancement in an individual's age, passing through certain stages in sequential order. Psychologists and behavior scientists have come up with different stages to explain how an individual's personality develops.

A. Sigmund Freud's stages of personality

1. The oral stage (0-1 year)
The oral stage lasts for the first year of one's life. It is the infancy stage of personality development. The stimulation given to the infant, both in excessive and inadequate amounts, makes the infant optimistic about the world.

2. The anal stage (2-3 year)
The anal stage extends throughout the second and third year of a child. This stage the anal becomes the gratification. The parents give training to the child gets reflection in adulthood behavior.
 3. The phallic stage (4-5 years)
The phallic stage develops at the age of four years. This stage is also characterized as the stage of psychosexual development. The children in this age can be observed examining and fondling their genitalia and enjoying matters of birth.
 4. The latency stage (6-7 years)
The latency stage children's are interested in seeking gratification of the libido from the external sources, knowledge and alike. Hence this period has long lasting effects in ones personality and it shaping in a definite pattern.
 5. The genital stage
In this stage adulthood occurs the genital stage the sexual drive in this stage. The genital stage in psychoanalytic is the term used by Freud to described the final stage of human psychosexual development, the individual develops a strong sexual interest in people outside of the family.
4. School age- (5-12)
The child joins school from age 5 to 12 years he / she learns knowledge and skills. If the child makes progress with his / her abilities it develops in child a sence of indusing. The opposite results in a sence of inferiority.
 5. Adolescence (13-19)
The children during this stage try to gain a sence of identify for them in the society they do not want to become confused about themselves who they are.
 6. Young adulthood- (20-40)
The young during their try to develop deep and permanent relationship with others to have a feeling of intimacy failing in a sence of isolation.
 7. Adulthood- (40-65)
The adulthood of their age face the situation the adult generativity adults who are productive in work raise children with series concern and guide next generation.
 8. old (65 death).
The adult of integrity gains a sence of wistorn. He appreciates continuity of past presents and future and becomes fully satisfied.

B. Eriksons eight life stages -

Eriksons stages of psychosocial developments as articulated is a comprehensive.

1. Infancy- (0-2)
The first year of life of a person is characterized by trust vs arristrust. The infants raised loving and affection atmosphere learn to trust others this bears long irripact on ones personality
2. Early childhood (2-4)
In early childhood discover our body during this period the child starts to acquired independence when the child is allowed to it hel she feels outonomy. If disallowed a sence of shame and doubt develops in the child.
3. Play age- (4-5)
The child seeks to discover what can be done if the child is allowed and encouraged to do what he /she wants to do the child developers sence of initiative. Alternatively if the child is discouraged to do lack feels lack self confidence.

Conclusion-

from the in-depth review of past studies on personality development it can be concluded that most of the theories to measure of an individual interaction with its sub-systems like environment and situation.

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